

1 **Splicing factors are therapeutic targets in lymph node metastasis.**

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6 Lymph node metastasis is a strong indicator or predictor of dissemination to distant sites (metastasis to
7 the brain, lungs and liver) in cancer. We measured total transcription in metastasis to the lymph nodes to
8 understand the fundamental drivers of biological function in disease progression in humans with cancer
9 and discovered splicing machinery among the most abundantly expressed mRNAs in the lymph node
10 metastasis. In humans with breast cancer, the pre-mRNA processing factor 19 *PRPF19* was activated in
11 lymph node metastasis. In humans with lung cancer, the splicing factor *SRSF10* was activated in lymph
12 node metastasis. In each case, high tumor expression of splicing factor correlated with inferior overall
13 survival in lymph node positive but not lymph node negative patients. These data reveal splicing as a
14 therapeutic vulnerability in humans with solid tumors.
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Results

We measured total transcription in humans with lymph node metastasis to discover novel therapeutic targets to control disease progression.

Figure 1: In humans with breast cancer, the splicing factor *PRPF19* is activated in lymph node metastasis.

GSE44408

n=18 primary tumor; human breast cancer

n=16 lymph node metastasis; human breast cancer

probe ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
203103_s_at	1.46E-01	-1.4892853	-5.07757	-0.17901423	PRPF19	3229/22277	85.5

GSE57968

n=36 primary tumor; human breast cancer

n=36 lymph node metastasis; human breast cancer

probe ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
203103_s_at	9.07E-02	-1.714663	-4.63287	-0.1383658	PRPF19	3214/22277	99.0

Figure 2: In humans with lung cancer, the splicing factor *SRSF10* is activated in lymph node metastasis.

GSE235634

n=2 primary tumor; non-small cell lung cancer

n=2 lymph node metastasis; non-small cell lung cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
10772	3.36E-01	0.782	-0.9626261	-0.753146	429.11	SRSF10	2980/20667	85.6

GSE162102

n=2 primary tumor; small cell lung cancer

n=4 lymph node metastasis; small cell lung cancer

probe ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
A_23_P352291	3.79E-02	-2.46	-3.90359	-1.34319867	SRSF10	5049/58341	91.3

Figure 3: Splicing machinery differentially expressed in the lymph node metastasis is correlated with inferior overall survival in lymph node positive not not lymph node negative patients.

I. PRPF19

a. All patients

High PRPF19 Expression: 120 months
Low PRPF19 Expression: 78 months

b. Lymph Node positive

c. Lymph Node negative

High PRPF19 Expression: 118.03 months
Low PRPF19 Expression: 197.62 months

1 II. SRSF10

2
3 a. All

High SRSF10 Expression: 92.63 months
Low SRSF10 Expression: 55.37 months

11 b. N0

19 c. N1

d. N2

High SRSF10 Expression: 8 months
Low SRSF10 Expression: 21 months

Discussion

The data point to splicing as a fundamental vulnerability in lymph node metastasis, and thus disease progression in human cancer, at the systems level.